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Research Article

**DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF SPHERICAL
AGGLOMERATED CRYSTALS LOADED FAST DISOLVING
TABLETS FOR ENHANCING THE SOLUBILITY OF
MEFENAMIC ACID****K.Ashok * and M.V. Nagabhushanam,**¹ Department of Pharmaceutics, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Nagarjunanagar-522510.² Department of Pharmaceutics, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Guntur-522002**Abstract:**

The objective of the present work was to study the effect of different polymers on the solubility and dissolution rate of Mefenamic acid a poorly water soluble NSAIDs, by spherically agglomeration using methanol, water and dichloromethane as good solvent, poor solvent and bridging liquid, respectively. The quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion technique was used as a method for spherical agglomeration. Spherical agglomeration of Mefenamic acid were prepared by using Poloxamer -F338 and Gelucire 48/16 in the ratio of 1:0.5, 1:0.75, 1:1. The agglomerates were subjected to various physicochemical evaluations such as practical yield, drug content, solubility, flow properties, average particle size, scanning electron microscopy and dissolution studies. The optical electron microscopy studies showed that the agglomerates possesses a good spherical shape. This study, demonstrated that the successful development of directly compressible spherical agglomerates of Mefenamic acid prepared with selected carriers enhances the in-vitro dissolution property of Mefenamic acid, which could provide rapid onset of action and potentially increases oral bioavailability. To study the influence of co-processed superdisintegrants on performance of Mefenamic acid Fast dissolving tablets, a set of three formulations (F₇, F₈, F₉) were prepared using co-processed superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium: Crospovidone) in three different ratios 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 respectively. The formulation prepared with co-processed superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium: Crospovidone) in 1:3 ratio (F₉) was offered relatively rapid release of Mefenamic acid when compared with other ratios employed in this investigation.

Key words: Mefenamic acid, Poloxamer -F338, Gelucire 48/16, spherically agglomeration**Corresponding author:****K.Ashok,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Mefenamic acid is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) used for relief of signs and symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis and is used in chronic and acute conditions of pain and inflammation. As its serum concentrations and analgesic effect are correlated, rapid absorption of Mefenamic acid could be a prerequisite for the quick onset of its action. The major problem with drug is its very low solubility in biological fluids, gastric irritation and its short biological half-life of 2 h. It is practically insoluble in water and so possesses poor solubility and subsequent poor GI absorption and bioavailability. Thus rapid Mefenamic acid absorption could be a prerequisite for the quick onset of its action. Because of its high membrane permeability characteristic, extent of Mefenamic acid absorption approaches up to 100%. Therefore, dissolution becomes the rate limiting step for absorption and the quick release of Mefenamic acid in the gastrointestinal tract following oral administration is desirable. The major problem of Mefenamic acid is its very low water solubility, which results into poor dissolution rate. The purpose of the present work was to improve the solubility, dissolution rate and micromeritic properties of Mefenamic acid through spherical crystallization by quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion technique [1-2]. The resultant crystals can be designated as spherical agglomerates. Spherical crystallization is an effective alternative to improve dissolution rate of drugs. This can be achieved by various methods such as spherical agglomeration, quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion and neutralization methods. Many of the drugs, evolving from these techniques, can be categorized as class II

drugs according to Biopharmaceutical classification system. These drugs are poorly water soluble, but once they are dissolved they are easily absorbed through the gastrointestinal membrane. Therefore, bioavailability after oral administration can be improved by enhancement of the dissolution rate. One of the approaches to dissolution rate is use of spherical crystallization technique [3-6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Mefenamic acid was obtained from Dr.Reddy's labs, Hyderabad, India. Poloxamer -F338 and Gelucire 48/16 were purchased from SD fine Chemicals Ltd, Mumbai. All other materials used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Spherically Agglomerates:

All spherical agglomerates were obtained by the quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method [7]. Spherical agglomerates were prepared with and without stabilizers by spherical crystallization technique. The stabilizers composition was given in Table 1. Mefenamic acid (1.0 g) was dissolved in good solvent N,N-dimethylformamide (25.0 mL). The bridging liquid chloroform (12.5 mL) was added to it. The resulting solution was then poured drop wise into the poor solvent distilled water (100 mL) containing different surfactant like, Poloxamer -F338 and Gelucire 48/16 with a stirring rate of 500 rpm using propeller type agitator (Remi Motors Ltd., Mumbai, India) at room temperature [8]. After agitating the system for 30 minutes, the prepared agglomerates were collected by filtration through Whatmann filter paper no.42.

Table 1: Composition of Mefenamic acid Spherical Agglomerates

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Mefenamic acid (g)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Poloxamer -F338 (g)	0.5	0.75	1			
Gelucire 48/16 (g)				0.5	0.75	1
N,N-dimethylformamide	25	25	25	25	25	25
Dichloromethane(ml)	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Water (ml)	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5

Evaluation of spherical agglomerates:**a) Particle size determination:**

Particle size determination was carried out using optical microscopy with a calibrated eye piece micrometer and stage micrometer by taking a small quantity of formulation on slide⁸. About 100 spherical agglomerates size was measured individually, average was taken and their size range and mean diameter frequency was calculated. Average Particle size is calculated by the following formula, Average Particle size = $\sum d/n$

b) Drug Content Estimation:

The percentage drug content in spherical agglomerates was estimated by dissolving spherical agglomerates equivalent to 100 mg of Mefenamic acid in methanol, mixed thoroughly by shaking and the volume was made up to the mark with in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was diluted suitably with 6.8 pH phosphate buffer and absorbance was measured at 279 nm using UV/Visible spectrophotometer [9].

c) Dissolution studies of agglomerates:

In-vitro dissolution studies of pure drug and spherical agglomerates were carried out for 60 minutes using USP Dissolution test apparatus type II (Lab India DISSO 2000, eight stages) at 50 rpm. Spherical agglomerates equivalent to 100 mg of Mefenamic acid was used for dissolution study at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ \text{C}$ in 900 ml of 6.8 pH phosphate buffer as dissolution medium. Aliquot equal to 5 ml was withdrawn at regular time intervals (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 min), an equal volume of fresh dissolution medium was replaced to maintain the sink condition and aliquots were measured at 279 nm UV/Visible spectrophotometer. $DE_{30\%}$, T_{50} , T_{90} and k^{-1} values were calculated from dissolution data [10].

Preparation of Mefenamic acid tablets:

To study the influence of co-processed superdisintegrants on performance of Mefenamic acid Fast dissolving tablets, a set of three formulations (F₇, F₈, F₉) were prepared using co-processed superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium: Crospovidone) in three different ratios 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 respectively. Tablets were made from blends by direct compression method. All the ingredients ingredients (shown in Table 3) were mixed [11]. The resulting blend was lubricated with magnesium stearate and compressed into tablets using the Cadmach single punch (round shaped, 7mm thick) machine.

Evaluation of Mefenamic Acid Tablets**a) Weight variation test [12]:**

Weight variation test was done by weighing 20 tablets individually, calculating the average weight and comparing the individual tablet weight to the average weight.

b) Drug content [13]:

Twenty tablets were powdered, and powder equivalent to 100 mg of Mefenamic acid was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Initially, 5 ml methanol was added and shaken for 10 min. Then, the volume was made up to 100 ml with 6.8 phosphate buffer. The solution in the volumetric flask was filtered, diluted suitably and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 279 nm.

c) Disintegration Time [14]:

The disintegration time was determined in distilled water at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ \text{C}$ using disintegration test apparatus USP ED-2L (Electro lab, Mumbai).

d) Friability [14]:

Roche friabilator was used to determine the friability. Pre weighed tablets were placed in friabilator and rotated at a speed of 25 rpm for 4 minutes or up to 100 revolutions. The tablets are dropped from a distance of 6 inches in each revolution. The tablets were then reweighed after removal of fines and the percentage of weight loss was calculated.

$$\% \text{ friability} = \frac{\text{Weight before friabilati on} - \text{Weight after friabilati on}}{\text{Weight before friabilati on}} \times 100$$

e) Hardness [14]: Hardness of the tablet was determined using the Monsanto hardness tester. The lower plunger was placed in contact with the tablet and a zero reading was taken. The plunger was then forced against a spring by tuning threaded bolts until the tablet fractured. Then the final reading was recorded. The hardness was computed by deducting the initial pressure from the final pressure.

f) Wetting Time [14]: The wetting time of the tablets can be measured using a simple procedure. Five circular tissue papers of 10 cm diameter are placed in a petridish with a 10 cm diameter. 10 mL of water-containing amaranth a water soluble dye is added to petridish. A tablet is carefully placed on the surface of the tissue paper. The time required for water to reach upper surface of the tablet is noted as a wetting time.

g) *In vitro* dispersion time [14]: Tablet was added to 10 ml of phosphate buffer solution pH 6.8 (pH of saliva) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Time required for complete dispersion of tablet was measured.

h) Fineness of dispersion [14]: This test was performed by placing two tablets in 100 ml of water and stirring it gently, until the tablets get completely disintegrated. Then the dispersion is passed through a sieve screen with a nominal mesh aperture of 710 μm .

j) Dissolution studies [14]:

Dissolution studies for Mefenamic acid fast dissolving tablets were performed in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer using USP dissolution test apparatus (Electrolab, Mumbai, India) with a paddle stirrer. The paddles are allowed to rotate at speed of 100 rpm. The dissolution medium was maintained at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and samples are withdrawn at an interval of every 5 min the volume of the withdrawn samples are replaced by fresh dissolution medium in order to keep the volume of the dissolution medium as constant. The withdrawn samples are filtered and absorbance was measured at absorption maxima of 279 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer.

k) In-vitro dissolution kinetic studies [14]:

The drug release data were plotted and tested with zero order (cumulative % drug released Vs time), First order (Log % remained Vs time). The in vitro dissolution kinetic parameters, dissolution rate constants (K), correlation coefficient (r), the times (t_{50}) for 50 % drug released (half-life) and dissolution efficiency [D.E.] were calculated. From the slopes of linear plots, the dissolution rates were calculated.

l) FTIR (Fourier Transform Infra-red Spectroscopy) Studies [15]:

Infrared (IR) spectroscopy studies of Mefenamic acid and its optimized formulations with PVP and cross povidone were recorded in a FTIR spectrophotometer (Thermo-IR 200) Potassium bromide pellet method was employed and background spectrum was collected under identical conditions. The spectrum for each sample showed the wavelength of absorbed light which is a characteristic of the chemical bonds in the sample. Each spectrum was derived from 16 single average scans collected in the region of 400 - 4000 cm^{-1} at a spectral resolution of 2 cm^{-1} .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Spherical agglomerates of Mefenamic acid were prepared by quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method (QESD) using a three solvent system. It involves

good solvent, poor solvent and a bridging liquid. The selection of these solvents depends on the miscibility of the solvents and the solubility of drug in individual solvent. Accordingly methanol, dichloromethane, water were selected as a good solvent, bridging liquid, and poor solvent, respectively. Mefenamic acid is highly soluble in methanol, but poorly soluble in water. Also it is soluble in dichloromethane which is immiscible in water. Hence, this solvent system was used in the present study. In QESD method, when good solvent solution of drug plus bridging liquid were poured in the poor solvent (containing different carriers) under agitation, quasi emulsion droplets of bridging liquid and good solvent were produced. Then the good solvent diffuses gradually out of the emulsion droplet into the outer poor solvent phase. The counter-diffusion of the poor solvent into the droplets induces the crystallization of the drug within the droplet due to the decrease in solubility of the drug in the droplet containing the poor solvent. The bridging liquid wets the crystal surface to cause binding and promotes the formation of liquid bridges between the drug crystals to form spherical agglomerates. The spherically agglomerated crystals are formed by coalescence of these dispersed crystals. In the present study effect of different polymers on solubility and dissolution rate of spherical agglomerates of Mefenamic acid were studied. Incorporation of polymer during agglomeration significantly enhanced the dissolution. Mixing of drug with a carrier results in greater wetting and increase surface available for dissolution by reducing interfacial tension between the hydrophilic drug and dissolution media. It was noted that drug carrier system sink immediately, while pure drug keeps floating on the surface for a longer time interval. The cumulative percentage of drug released from different agglomerates was increased in the following order: Mefenamic acid spherical agglomerates prepared with Poloxamer -F338 > Mefenamic acid spherical agglomerates prepared with Gelucire 48/16. Among all the formulations prepared, spherical agglomerates prepared Mefenamic acid and Poloxamer -F338 in 1:1 ratio showed highest drug release in 60 minutes.

To study the influence of co-processed superdisintegrants on performance of Mefenamic acid Fast dissolving tablets, a set of three formulations (F₇, F₈, F₉) were prepared using co-processed superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium: Crospovidone) in three different ratios 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 respectively. The dissolution rate followed first-order kinetics as the graphs drawn between log % drug unreleased vs time were found to be linear. The dissolution rate of Mefenamic acid was found to

be effected by nature of the superdisintegrant used in the preparation of tablets. The formulation prepared with co-processed superdisintegrants (Croscarmallose sodium: Crospovidone) in 1:3 ratio (F₉) was offered

relatively rapid release of Mefenamic acid when compared with other ratios employed in this investigation.

Table 2: Particle size and % of Drug content of Mefenamic acid spherical agglomerates

Formulation	Particle size(μm)	% of Drug content
F1	215	98.18
F2	247	97.63
F3	267	97.23
F4	276	98.44
F5	293	97.14
F6	312	96.27

Table 3: *In-vitro* dissolution kinetics of Mefenamic acid spherical crystals prepared with different carriers.

S.No.	Formulation	T ₅₀ (min)	T ₉₀ (min)	DE ₃₀ (%)	K (min ⁻¹)	Correlation coefficient values	
						Zero Order	First order
1	F ₁	22.1	73.5	30.59	0.0313	0.9710	0.9814
2	F ₂	19.1	63.4	34.29	0.0363	0.9568	0.9785
3	F ₃	16.2	53.9	37.34	0.0427	0.9460	0.9704
4	F ₄	25.3	84.0	27.00	0.0274	0.9821	0.9835
5	F ₅	22.01	73.20	30.74	0.0315	0.9703	0.9816
6	F ₆	19.6	65.01	33.42	0.0354	0.9612	0.9810

Table 4: Composition of ingredients for Mefenamic acid fast dissolving tablets

S.No	Ingredients	F 7	F8	F9
1	Mefenamic acid crystals prepared with Poloxomer -F338 in 1:1 ratio	200	200	200
2	Croscarmallose sodium+ Crospovidone	15	15	15
3	Micro crystalline cellulose	81	81	81
4	Talc	2	2	2
5	Magnesium streate	2	2	2
	Total weight	300	300	300

Table 5: Physical parameters of Mefenamic acid fast dissolving tablets

S.No.	Parameters	F ₇	F ₈	F ₉
1	Average weight (mg)	298 \pm 0.2	299 \pm 0.1	300 \pm 0.2
2	Drug content (%)	98.3	99.8	97.9
3	Disintegration time (sec)	154	141	121
4	Friability (%)	0.24	0.45	0.43
5	Hardness (kg/sqcm)	4.2	4.2	3.8
6	Wetting time (sec)	131	123	97
7	<i>In-vitro</i> dispersion time (min)	256	214	164
8	Fineness of dispersion	pass	pass	pass

Table 6: *In-vitro* dissolution kinetics of Mefenamic acid fast dissolving tablets

S.No.	Formulation	T ₅₀ (min)	T ₉₀ (min)	DE ₁₅ (%)	K (min ⁻¹)	Correlation coefficient values	
						Zero Order	First order
1	F ₇	6.0	20.1	48.78	0.115	0.8493	0.9751
2	F ₈	4.7	15.6	56.37	0.148	0.8268	0.9762
3	F ₉	3.1	10.3	66.31	0.222	0.8049	0.9833

Figure 1: *In-vitro* dissolution profile of Mefenamic acid fast dissolving tablets with coprocessed superdisintegrants

(-♦-) Mefenamic acid pure drug

(-■-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:1 ratio by coprocessing technique

(-▲-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:2 ratio by coprocessing technique

(-×-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:3 ratio by coprocessing technique

Figure 2: First order plots of Mefenamic acid tablets with coprocessed superdisintegrants

(-♦-) Mefenamic acid pure drug

(-■-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:1 ratio by coprocessing technique

(-▲-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:2 ratio by coprocessing technique

(-×-) Mefenamic acid tablets prepared with crospovidone and croscarmallosesodium in 1:3 ratio by coprocessing technique

CONCLUSION:

Present study concluded that spherical agglomerates prepared by the quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method showed an improvement in the solubility, dissolution rate, compactibility, wettability, flowability and bioavailability. These spherical agglomerates also showed excellent physico-chemical characters as compared with plain drug which indicates that the spherical agglomerates can suitable for directly compressible tablet process .

REFERENCES:

1. Indian Pharmacopoeia, Vol II, Govt. of India, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, New Delhi, The controller of Publications, 2010; 1479-83.
2. Tripathi K D. NSAIDs .In, Tripathi K D(ed). Essentials of Pharmacology, 6th edition, New delhi, Jaypee Publication,;184-201
3. Guillaume F., Guyot-Hermann A.M., Guyot J.C., Spherical crystallization of meprobamate, *Il Farmaco.*, 1993; 48: 73-485.
4. Di Martino P., Barthelemy C., Piva F., Joiris E., Palmieri G.F., Martelli S., Improved dissolution behavior of fenbufen by spherical crystallization, *Drug Dev.Ind.Pharm.*,1999; 25:1073-081.
5. Akbuga J., Preparation and evaluation of controlled release furosemide microspheres by spherical crystallization, *Int. J.Pharm.*,1989; 53:99-105.
6. Ribardie`re A., Tchoreloff P., Couarraze G., Puisieux F., Modification of ketoprofen bead structure produced by the spherical crystallization technique with a two-solvent system, *Int. J. Pharm.*,1996; 144: 195-207.
7. Sanjeev Kumar , Pradeep Kumar, Chanderparkash, Shailendra K Singh. Evaluation of Some Novel Techniques For Dissolution Enhancement of Poorly Water Soluble Drug Nimodipine. *International Journal of PharmTech Research.* 2010 ;2(1): 950-959.
8. Tapan Kumar Giri, Hemant Badwaik, Amit Alexander , Dulal Krishna Tripathi . Solubility enhancement of Mefenamic acid in the presence of hydrophilic polymer and surfactant. *Int j applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology* 2009; 2(2):119-130.
9. Ranjit Dash, Ajit Kumar Acharya, Sanysi Swain, Mayank Barg, Hemant Kumar Choudhary, Khageswar Meher. Formulation and Evaluation of Spherical Crystal of Etoricoxib. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical & Biological Archives* 2011; 2(4):1123-1129.
10. Goczo H, Szabo-Revesz P, Farkas B, Hasznos-Nezdei M, Serwanis SF, Pintye-Hodi AK., Development of spherical crystals of Acetyl salicylic

acid for direct tablet making, *Chem.Pharm. Bull.*, 2000, 48, 1877-81.

11. Di Martino P, Barthélémy C, Piva F, Joiris E, Palmieri GF, Martelli S., Improved dissolution behavior of fenbufen by spherical crystallization, *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.*, 1999, 25, 1073-81.

12. Battue S K, Repay M.A, Maunder S , Rio M Y. Formulation and evaluation of rapidly disintegrating tablet Fenoverine tablets: Effect of superdisintegrants. *Drug. Dev. Ind. Pharm* 2007;33: 1225-1232.

13. Sunada H , Yonezawa Y, Danjo K, Otsuka A , Iida K . Preparation and evaluation of a compressed tablet rapidly disintegrating in the oral cavity. *Chem Pharm Bull (Tokyo)* 1996 ; 44: 2121-2127 .

14. Gohel.M.C, Bansal.G, Bhatt.N, Formulation and evaluation of orodispersible taste masked tablets of Famotidine. *Pharma Boil world* 2005;3: 75-80.

15. Sunil Kumar J, Meenakshi S, Vivek S. Development and in Vitro Evaluation of Mefenamic acid Mouth Dissolving Tablets Using Solid Dispersion Technique. *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* 2010; 58(8): 1037—1042.